

THE ROLE OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS IN EDUCATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7996918>

Annotation: We know that physical education, among all areas, is now being paid more attention by our government than ever before. This is one of the tools that plays an important role in education, personality psyche, maturation. The article reflects on the role of physical education and sports in education.

Key words: physical education, sports, education, personality psyche, mental education, aesthetic education, labor education, training.

Physical education and sports are considered an important process in the development of personality, which includes such important factors as comprehensive education, wellness and training for Labor.

The social significance of physical education should be understood by the following connections and tasks: it is possible to briefly influence its connection with mental, aesthetic and labor education.

Physical Education serves in the development of mental education, depending on the content and direction of each area or process. For example: in sports or artists' (ballet) figure skating on ice, it is to feel mentally controlled that they know the directions and how many turns.

The social essence of physical education is understood as an increase in the ability to work. This provides for production Gymnastics, various exercises during intermediate breaks-Games, sports training on the day of rest, trips and other direct services.

The role of physical education in the implementation of aesthetic education has its own characteristics. It is expressed in such games as dances, ballet, circus, percussion. In the art of singing, physical exercises are also widely used in the ways of deepening breathing, tempering the throat passages with fresh air.

In order to improve health from physical education and sports, the health-improving forces of nature (water, air, sun) and hygienic requirements are fully observed. For this reason, from the embodiment of natural and special processes associated with human activity in the socio-educational characteristics of physical education and sports.

In the socio-educational features of physical education and sports, wellness activities are a socio-pedagogical process that plays an important role. On this basis, the training of qualified personnel in the field of physical education and sports is an important process that is subject to state education. This, in turn, is associated with the satisfaction of needs in the physical education and sports movement, further improving the socio-cultural conditions of the population. Along the way, the activities carried out by the president and the Government of the Republic pay off at a high level. For this reason, the number of people involved in one

form or another of physical education and sports is increasing in all segments of the population.

In our country, serious attention is paid to the work of educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism, and above all, great attention is paid to strengthening ojd work in neighborhoods, educational institutions, production enterprises, institutions.

In the above directions, in the content of Military-Physical Training activities, physical exercises, Sports, Travel (Tourism-finding, marking, etc.k.) and targeted use of folk National Games. Some of them can be given a brief description:

1. Physical education classes. The content of physical education classes, which are held in the upper classes of general educational schools and secondary special and higher educational institutions, is mainly focused on the physical perfection and conditioning of students-young people. It uses elements of gymnastics, athletics, water swimming, wrestling and other sports.

2. Physical conditioning also has a place in the content of special technical and tactical training in pre-military training classes. In this case, pull-ups, hang-ups, spins, middle-and long-distance running, swimming in the water, wrist strength testing, jumping obstacles and other exercises are widely used on the turnstile.

3. At military call points (district-city military districts), an exercise is organized to test physical fitness and train prospective soldiers in special physical training.

4. Depending on the military units, types in units and specialties, Military-Physical Training is carried out.

5. Regular physical fitness training exercises with officers and senior officers.

In youth, a reserve of all physical abilities becomes available. To do this, rational and regular pedagogical influences should be encouraged. Pedagogical impact on the development of the physical abilities of young athletes the growth in one step or another of the age-appropriate development process contributes to the full manifestation of the most vividly expressed abilities.

With the use of low-intensity aerobic loads, the results achieved with extremely intense loads, which lead to excessive strain of physiological activities, can also be achieved with the help of optimal means for the body.

The main purpose of Military-Physical Training in the above directions is that, in addition to the use of Military-Physical Training of personnel and soldiers for the defense of the motherland, it is also aimed at ensuring the health of the personal composition and all members. These aspects, in turn, mobilize the responsibility of each servant and soldier to increase, faithfully fulfill his duties to the motherland and the people. These are the tools of physical education-of (exercise Games, sports, etc.k.) as evidenced by its socio-educational significance. For this reason, it is necessary for the student to make it a habit for young people and students to regularly engage in physical education and sports in educational processes. It is also necessary to study the importance of physical education and sports in military-physical training, to find ways to instill them in young people.

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